

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR:

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by:

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24-25 May 2023

Bragança, Portugal

PRIMA
PARTNERSHIP FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

Centro de
Investigação
de Montanha

Published in Bragança, Portugal
May, 2023

Title

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Printed by

BRINGRÁFICA Indústrias Gráficas, LDA
Rua Arquiteto Viana de Lima, nº 53
5300-678 Bragança

Publisher

Instituto Politécnico de Bragança
Campus de Santa Apolónia
5300-253 Bragança
Portugal

Edition year: 2023

ISBN: 978-972-745-320-7 (Electronic version)

Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/10198/1787>

URL: <https://esa.ipb.pt/artisanefood-seminar>

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Genomic and Phenotypic Analysis of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from *Alheira*, a Portuguese Traditional Fermented Sausage

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Abstract

Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) play a crucial role in determining the flavour, texture, and nutritional properties of fermented foods. This study aimed to investigate the diversity of LAB in *alheira*, a traditional Portuguese fermented meat sausage. For this, 63 LAB isolates were obtained from 28 *alheira* samples collected from different regions of Portugal, including Vimioso, Mirandela, Vinhais, Mogadouro, Pova de Lila, Bragança, and Valpaços. The LAB isolates were reactivated in Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe or M17 agar and then subjected to molecular identification using the 16S ribosomal gene. Genomic DNA extraction was carried out with the GF-1 Bacterial DNA Extraction Kit, and amplification of the 16S gene was performed by 27f (5'-AGA GTT TGA TCC TGG CTC AG-3') and 1492r (5'-CTA CGG CTA CCT TGT TAC GA-3') primers. The sequencing reactions were made with BigDye™ Terminator v3.1, and samples were purified with SAM/BigDyeXTerminator™ bead solution. Capillary electrophoresis was conducted with the SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer. The BLAST algorithm was used to obtain alignments with at least 97% identity with reference sequences from the NCBI database. In addition to molecular identification, the LAB isolates were also evaluated for *in-vitro* proteolytic activity (mm), L-lactic acid (g/L), acidifying capacity, and antimicrobial capacity against *Salmonella* Typhimurium, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The data obtained were assessed by Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Genetic analysis of samples revealed a diverse LAB population, *Enterococcus* was the most abundant genus (31.7%), followed by *Leuconostoc* (19%) and *Lactilactobacillus* (17.5%). The acidification was mainly contributed by *Enterococcus* (*E. faecium* and *E. durans*), while *Leuconostoc*, *Pediococcus*, and *Lactiplantibacillus* exhibited higher inhibition diameters values against *S. Typhimurium* (PC1=58%, PC2=19.3%), *L. monocytogenes* (PC1=53.9%, PC2=19.4%), and *S. aureus* (PC1=56.3%, PC2=18.5%) in addition to high proteolytic activity, as revealed by the PCA analysis. Finally, the results indicated that *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* was the LAB species with higher inhibitory effects against the three pathogens analysed. These results indicate that a comprehensive characterisation of LAB can be valuable for improving food safety and quality control.

Keywords: non-RTE sausages; food biotechnology; molecular identification.

Supporting Funds: Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) through FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). EU PRIMA programme, FCT for funding the ArtiSaneFood project (PRIMA/0001/2018).